

FUNCTIONALIZED MAGNETIC NANOPARTICLES FOR SELECTIVE TARGETING OF CELLS

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Magnetic metal oxide nanoparticles were conjugated to single stranded DNA (ssDNA), and Cytosin-phosphatidyl-Guanosin oligonucleotide (CpG ODN) to detect and activate Toll-like (TLR9) receptors in cells and to follow nanoparticle cellular trafficking by different ways of imaging while at the same time serving as a drug carrier system. By virtue of their magnetic properties these nanoparticles may serve as vehicles for the transport of target molecules into cells, while the fluorescent target ligand allows optical detection simultaneously.

INTRODUCTION

One of the difficult aspects of developing an *in vivo* approach to cancer treatment is the specific targeting of cancer cells. One strategy is the use of therapeutic nucleotides. Microbial pathogens that penetrate epithelial barriers and invade tissues are usually encountered by three types of sentinel immune cells: tissue macrophages, mast cells and immature dendritic cells. These sentinels must be able to distinguish between fragments of apoptotic cells generated during normal tissue turnover and particles that are indicative of microbial assaults and infections. The molecules responsible for making this pivotal distinction belong to the family of pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), of which Toll-like receptors (TLRs) are best characterized [1]. TLRs recognize highly conserved microbial structures that were termed pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). Stimulation of macrophages or mast cells through their TLRs leads to the synthesis and secretion of proinflammatory cytokines and lipid mediators, thereby initiating an inflammatory response that recruits both soluble immune components and immune cells from the blood [2]. On the other hand, TLR stimulation of dendritic cells induces the initiation of an adaptive immune response [3].

One of the exciting new research subjects involving magnetic nanoparticles is their application in biological systems, including targeted drug delivery, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), biosensors and magnetic hyperthermia therapy. Nanoparticles are attractive probe candidates because of their (i) small size (1-50 nm) and correspondingly large surface-to-volume ratio, (ii) chemically tailorable physical properties which directly relate to size, composition, and shape, (iii) unusual target binding properties, and (iv) overall structural robustness. The size of a nanomaterial can be an advantage over a bulk structure, because a target binding event involving the nanomaterial can have a significant effect on its physical and chemical properties, thereby providing a mode of signal transduction not necessarily available with a bulk structure made of the same material.

We have designed a pathogen-mimicking metal oxide nanoparticle with the ability to enter cancer cells and selectively target and activate the TLR9 pathway, in addition to optical and MR imaging capabilities. The immobilization of ssDNA or CpG-ODN on Fe₂O₃ and MnO nanoparticles was performed via a multifunctional polymer

used for the nanoparticle surface modification. The polymer coating not only affords a protective organic biocompatible shell but also provides an efficient and convenient means for loading immunostimulatory oligonucleotides.

EXPERIMENT

Iron oxide and manganese oxide nanoparticles were synthesized according to ref. [4,5]. Phase identification of the naked manganese oxide nanoparticles was carried out using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (on a Philips 420 instrument with an acceleration voltage of 120 kV or on a Philips TECNAI F30 electron microscope, field-emission gun, 300 kV extraction voltage) and X-ray powder diffraction (Siemens D8 powder diffractometer). The magnetic susceptibilities of samples were measured with a SQUID magnetometer (Quantum Design).

The particles were functionalized using a multidentate functional copolymer [5] carrying catecholate groups as surface binding ligands for the manganese oxide nanoparticles, a fluorescent dye for optical detection and free amino groups for the attachment of the target ligands. An aliquot MnO was treated with an appropriate amount of the reactive polymer dissolved in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF). To remove unbound polymer the coated magnetic particles in the solution were extracted by a magnetic particle concentrator (DynaL MPC1-50, Dynal Biotech, France) at room temperature. The isolated magnetic nanoparticles were washed with DMF ensuring the removal of unreacted polymer and subsequently dispersed in methyl imidazole buffer (MeIm, 0.1 M, pH 7.5). A portion of the washed magnetic particles was freeze-dried for subsequent characterization. The average crystallite size of the particles with and without the functional polymer coating was estimated using TEM.

The presence of primary amine groups on the surface-bound polymer ligand permits the attachment of reactive N-hydroxy-succinimide ester of porphyrin through peptide chemistry (experimental details are supplied in ESI). dsRNA CpG was obtained commercially (Sigma) and prepared to a final concentration of 2 mg/ml. dsRNA CpG contains phosphate groups at its 5' end which makes it susceptible to functionalization in the presence of a primary amine making use of phosphoramidate chemistry [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

XRD measurements of the as prepared manganese oxide show the formation of the MnO phase. This is further confirmed by TEM analysis. The MnO particles were prepared with sizes ranging from 6-25 nm, Figure 1 shows a sample of MnO nanoparticles with diameters of 7 nm. The hysteresis loops recorded at low temperature (10 K) showed large coercivities and large remanences typical for ferrimagnetic materials. Particles exhibit paramagnetism at room temperature. It has been recently reported that very small MnO nanoparticles (5–10 nm in diameter) show weak ferromagnetic behavior at low temperatures [4a], although bulk MnO shows antiferromagnetic behavior with $T_N = 125$ K. The observed weak ferromagnetism was ascribed to the presence of noncompensated surface spins on the antiferromagnetic core of the MnO nanoparticle [4a].

In this contribution we introduce a novel multifunctional polymeric ligand (Figure 2) to immobilize CpG ODN onto MnO nanoparticles that curbs the multistep tailoring of nanoparticle functionalization. The multifunctional polymeric ligand combines three

features: (i) an anchor group based on dopamine which is capable of binding to many metal oxides, [7] (ii) a fluorescent dye (as a marker) and (iii) a reactive functional group which allows binding of various biomolecules onto inorganic nanoparticles. CpG ODN contains a 5' end phosphate group which makes it amenable to bind to amine moieties by making use of phosphoramidate chemistry [6]. The biological activity of the CpG ODN coated magnetic nanoparticles was demonstrated on kidney cancer cells Caki-1 (human renal cell line). The specific binding of the nanoparticle CpG ODN complex to the cell receptors was proven experimentally as sketched in Figure 3.

Figure 1. Transmission electron microscopic (TEM) image of manganese oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 2. Multifunctional copolymer containing 3-hydroxytyramine (dopamine) as an anchor group for the binding of metal oxides, rhodamine, as a fluorophore, and a free amine group for the conjugation of ssDNA, CpG ODN.

The presence of TLR9 in Caki-1 cells was determined using NaDoSO₄. The correspondent protein identification and localization of receptors was achieved through western blotting and immunocytochemistry, respectively (Figure 3). TLR9 is known to be localized intracellularly and it comprises of a ligand-binding ectodomain and a cytoplasmatic portion which belongs to the Tol-IL-1 receptor (TIR) family of signalling domains [8]. The Caki-1 cells were lysed and the supernatant was analyzed using a standard gel electrophoresis procedure. A 12% NaDoSO₄ gel was used to separate the polypeptides, the proteins were transferred to a membrane and treated with monoclonal anti-TLR9 antibodies (1:500 dilution). The immunocomplexes were visualized after the incubation with anti-mouse IgG (*Fab*-specific) alkaline phosphatase produced in goat (1:1000) using a color developing system (NBT/BCIP). The western blotting analysis

shows a band of approximately 130 kDa, (Figure 3A), which is in agreement with the glycosylated molecular weight of TLR9 [9]. For the localization of TLR9 in the Caki-1 cells, an immunodetection technique was used (Figure 3B). Following methanol fixation, the cells were rehydrated and incubated with TLR9 mouse monoclonal antibody raised against human TLR9 (hTLR9), which in turn were conjugated with Cy-3-labeled anti-mouse IgG secondary antibody (Figure 5B). Subsequently, the cells were analyzed using optical light microscopy, with a reflected light fluorescence attachment at the emission wavelength of 456 (filter U) and 565 nm (filter G) to visualize the DAPI and the Cy-3 fluorophore, respectively (Figure 3B (b)). The permeabilization step using methanol was necessary to stain the intracellularly distributed TLR9. A red fluorescence signal was obtained due to Cy-3 -labelled secondary antibody, proving the presence of TLR9 in Caki-1 cells, in accordance with the NaDoSO₄/WB results. Control was performed by replacing the primary antibody with a blocking solution where no fluorescent signal was observed (Figure 3B (a)). We have shown that the TLR9 have a molecular weight of 130 kDa, owing to its glycosylated state, and is located intracellularly in Caki-1 cells suggesting its localization in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) as described for ssDNA-CpG unstimulated cells [10]. The internal localization of the TLR9 regulates the access to its ligands due to biological reasons [11].

Figure 3. Identification of Toll-like receptor 9 in Caki-1 cells by Western blotting (A). Cell lysate was prepared and separated by gel electrophoresis. The western blotting experiments the membrane was reacted with monoclonal antibodies raised against human TLR9. A clear band with a molecular weight of approximately 130 kDa can be identified. M: a size marker was run in parallel. Epifluorescent images of immunostaining of TLR9 in Caki-1 cells (B). TLR9 monoclonal antibody was used as well as the correspondent Cy3-fluorophore conjugated secondary antibody (red). The red fluorescence signal is clearly visualized in the Caki-1 cells. Controls were performed using blocking solution PBS/FCS (10% v/v) as replacement of the primary antibody. Nuclei were visualized by staining with 4,6-diamino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) (blue signal) (scale bar: 20 μ m).

FITC-CpG ODN conjugated-polymer functionalized MnO nanoparticles were incubated with Caki-1 cells (37 °C, 5% CO₂) for 24h to target and promote TLR9

mediated cascade activation. Figure 4 shows epifluorescent microscope images representative of the extent of DNA conjugated nanoparticles in the cytosol. Following incubation, the cells were analyzed with a reflected light fluorescence attachment at different emission wavelengths to visualize DAPI staining (blue fluorescent signal), polymer functionalized MnO nanoparticles (red fluorescent signal) and FITC-CpG ODN (green fluorescent signal). The colocalization of green/red fluorescence signals in Figure 4 results in an overlap of fluorescent signals supporting polymer functionalized MnO nanoparticles as efficient carriers of ssDNA for the Caki-1 cells. After 24h incubation the co-localized image shows an increased accumulation of FITC-CpG ODN loaded polymer functionalized nanoparticles into cellular compartments, which can now be attributed to lysosomes [10a].

Figure 4. Cellular uptake of MnO nanoparticles functionalized with rhodamine-polymer (red fluorescence) and coupled with FITC-CpG ODN (green fluorescence) at (A) 12 and (B) 24 h incubation. As controls, Caki-1 cells, polymer functionalized MnO nanoparticles and FITC-CpG ODN 2006 (soluble form) were analyzed in parallel. The cell nuclei were visualized by DAPI (blue). The specific binding between FITC-CpG ODN 2006 conjugated polymer functionalized MnO nanoparticles and TLR9 in Caki 1 cells activates signalling pathways resulting in I κ B α ubiquitination and consequently an immunomodulated response. (C) Western blotting analysis of Caki-1 cell lysate after 12 and 24 h incubation with polymer functionalized MnO nanoparticles (lane b and f), and ssDNA conjugated polymer functionalized MnO nanoparticles (lane c and g) was carried out to monitor the I κ B α degradation. As controls, cells lysates and Caki-1 cells incubated with ssDNA CpG ODN 2006 (soluble form) for 12 and 24 h (lane d and h) were used for comparison. M: molecular weight marker.

Interestingly, neither phosphodiester nor peptide bonds in the ssDNA CpG ODN coupled functionalized nanoparticles have been disrupted by lysosomal hydrolases. No green fluorescent signal randomly dispersed in the cytosol was visualized, demonstrating, polymer derivatized MnO nanoparticles to be an efficient cargo delivery system. The unspecific uptake was taken into consideration by using the polymer functionalized nanoparticles.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have designed the first pathogen-mimicking metal oxide nanoparticles with the ability to enter cancer cells and selectively target and activate the TLR9 pathway, in addition to optical and MR imaging capabilities. The multifunctional polymer used for the nanoparticle surface modification not only affords a protective organic biocompatible shell but also provides an efficient and convenient means for loading the immunostimulatory oligonucleotides. The development of versatile trimodal nanoparticles would allow a common user to follow nanoparticle cellular trafficking by different means of imaging and simultaneous use as drug effective carrier system. The generality of this approach should allow the design of nano-based therapeutics that can specifically target a wide range of diseased cells.

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